

**The Effect of Using Computer Media Based Web Blog
and Students' Creativity
on The Results of Students' English Learning**

Dini Hidayati
Post Graduate Program
Jakarta Islamic University
(dinisyrief@gmail.com)

Mulyadi
Post Graduate Program
Jakarta Islamic University
(mul_amir07@yahoo.com)

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to test : 1) The difference between the results of English learning for students who use computer media based web blog with the use of media power point, 2) The interaction between the use of computer media based web blog and creativity of students to the English learning outcomes, 3) The difference of English learning outcomes between students who learned with a computer media based web blog and power point on the students who have high creativity, 4) The difference of English learning outcomes between students who learned with a computer media based web blog and power point on the students who have low creativity.

This study used an experimental method. The population in this study were students in grade 7 totaling 7 classes of 252 students, 2 classes were taken as sample research that is one class as an experimental class and another class as control class. Experimental class of 35 students and the control class of 36 students. Each class is classified based on the creativity of high and low creativity.

The instrument used to obtain the data through computer media variable (A), the students' creativity (B), and English learning outcomes (Y). This analysis is done by Bivariate Pearson (Product Moment Correlation Pearson) by way of correlating each item score with the total score. Tests using two-sided tests with significance level of 0.05.

The results showed that: the English learning outcomes of student who learned with a computer media based web blog is higher than English learning outcomes of student who learned with power point media. Results of the study group of students who learned by the computer media based web blog is higher than students that learned with power point media. It is known through ANAVA two lanes visible $F\text{-Count} > F\text{-table} = 4.07$ or value sig. = 0.028 $< \alpha = 0:05$. 2) There is an Influence of the interaction between the media of learning, creativity of student to the learning outcomes. Results of analysis using two lane Anava test seen $F\text{ count} = 64.047 > F > F\text{-table} = 4.07$ or value sig. = 0.000 $< \alpha = 0:05$. This shows the truth that there is an influence of interaction between

learning media and creativity in learning to the learning outcomes of English Subject.

Key Words: computer media based web blog, students' creativity, English learning outcomes

A. Introduction

In teaching and learning activities, teachers' presence is not only limited to provide learning materials and to give home works, but the teacher demanded more and understand his job as designer of learning. Teachers must be able to develop the potential and creativity of learners. Based on the distribution of the final test result of each subjects, it is noted that the English test result is low compared to other subjects. The average result of the National Test for Junior High School 2017/2018 for English subject is 5.49 with maximum score is 9.90. The above fact encourage teachers to be wise in choosing teaching strategies.

The selection of the right learning media is the manifestation of the creativity of teachers so that students do not saturate in receiving lessons. Along with the development of information and communication technology these obstacles can be overcome. This demands a teacher should further improve insight, ability to educate and develop innovation and utilizing the media in the process of his teaching.

Teacher as a facilitator in learning should be able to develop innovations, particularly in the selection of media that will be used in the learning activities. One of them is a computer media based web blog. Through this medium students can access learning resources provided by teachers for the purposes of teaching and learning without limitation of time. Computer media based web blog is used to increase students' interest in reading.

Internet media should be able to be a medium that is able to enrich the students' content/literacy. So they do not just be a passive user, but being the person who became part of the educational content providers. The results of their study are not only read by the teacher, but can be accessed by the public. The existence of such facilities will motivate students in creating, honing and developing their competency. This kind of conditioning will produce human resource who are ready to compete in the era of globalization.

B. Literature Review

1. Understanding of Web Blog Media

According to Iwan Binanto weblog is a journal or periodical news which is updated on an ongoing basis by blog/blogger and intended for public consumption. Blog in general presents personality of the author in the website.

According to Marisa (2011), the blog is a type of website that contains content in the form of chronological sorted from newest posts at the top of the page to the delivery of the longest at the very bottom of the page.

Based on the above definitions, a blog is a great medium for pouring the writings that some one thought, and it's done not only for his own. Everybody can comment on or allowed to interact actively on what was written upon the permission of the owner of the blog.

Web blogs can be interpreted as a personal website run by blogger that contains the media to pour the writings which contain about the thoughts and views of something or it could be a journal of daily activities which can be accessed by everyone Ladiman (2012).

Media web blog in in this study is a computer media based web blog that is used as the media and learning resources that can be accessed by all students in the teaching and learning activities that are in the online area. The blog in this study is a blog that contains teacher work program, journals, materials, training information, develop literacy activities in teaching and learning process that can enhance student's creativity.

2. Characteristics of the Weblog Media

Web blogs media based on its characteristics including interactive media. According to Susilana (2008) the most important characteristics of this medium is that not only keeps the presentation or object, but also forced to interact during teaching and learning process. At least there are three kinds of interactions can be identified, namely:

1. The student interacts with a program, for example, filling out a text.
2. The students interact with a machine, e.g. learning machine, language laboratories, simulators, or terminal computer
3. Regulate the interactions between students regularly but not programmatic.

3. Types of Web Blogs

There are several types of blogs that can be used as media on the internet, namely:

1. Free Blog
This blog is a free blog that relies on owned hosting by blogging providers service. Some blog platforms that provide free blogging services are blogger / BlogSpot and WordPress.
2. Self-Hosting Blog
This blog model relies on private hosting or rented hosting. The advantage of this blog model is greater freedom of expression compared to free blogs.
3. Citizen Journalism Blog
This blog model just like a free blog. The difference from this blog model is only the purpose of the free blog provider service. If the free blog provider service can be used for any activity, in the citizen journalism blog model, its use is devoted to the delivery of news from and to the public Susamo (2010).

Media blogs that are used as media and learning resources at this study are free blogs and citizen journalism. The free blog web media that the author chose is free blogging service. The blog contains teaching device pages, teaching materials, writer's fiction works, coverage / news, information on teaching and

learning activities and extracurricular activities. Whereas citizen journalism developed is a compatanana with the same account name. In this citizen journalism media, the author specializes in presenting coverage on the activities of the author as a teacher, and other educational activities. These two media are often used by the author as a reference, the media in classrooms, especially those related to reading and writing material.

C. Research Methodology

1. Research Methods and Design

This research is quantitative research with experimental forms. The data analysis used is normality and homogeneity test, f count test with 2-way ANOVA using software of SPSS 20 Suharsimi (2006). Research Experiment Design can be described as in table 1 below. With the factorial design as follows:

Table 1: Factorial Research Design 2 x 2

Media (A) Creativity (B)	Web Blog (A1)	Power Point (A2)
Height (B1)	A1B1	A2B1
Low (B2)	A1B2	A2B2

Information:

A = learning media

B = Creativity

A1 = Web Blog Learning Media

A2 = Power Point learning media

B1 = Low Creativity

B2 = High Creativity

2. Populations and Samples

The populations of this study were seventh grade students of Junior High School totaling five classes of 180 students. Some of the five classes were taken to be used as research samples, two classes as experimental class and control class. The experimental class is 35 students and the control class is 36 students. The technique of taken sampling used in this study by using random sampling. Each class is classified based on high creativity and low creativity Widaryanto (2002).

3. Data Collection Techniques

The data used to find out the results of students' English learning is in the form of learning outcomes test, while to find out students' creativity is by giving questionnaires.

a. Calibration

Before this instrument is used, it is examined first through a pilot test. Instrument testing was conducted on students who were not included in the study sample. The quality of the instrument is indicated by the validity test and reliability to reveal what will be measured Sudjana (2006).

1. Validity

The validity test used with bicerial point, which uses the formula:

$$r_{p-bis} = \frac{\bar{x}_p - \bar{x}_t}{s_t} \sqrt{\frac{p}{q}}$$

2. Reliability

Instrument reliability is needed to obtain data in accordance with measurement objectives. To achieve this, reliability testing is performed using the following reliability coefficient:

$$r_i = \frac{K}{(K-1)} \left\{ \frac{S_t^2 - \sum p_i q_i}{S_t^2} \right\}$$

3. Statistics Hypothesis

The statistical hypothesis to be tested, namely

Ho: Zero hypothesis

HI: Alternative hypothesis

μ_{A1} : Average students' scores who take lessons with the computer media based web blog

μ_{A2} : Average of the students' score who take lessons with the power point media.

μ_{A1B1} : Average of the students' score who take lesson with the computer media based web blog with high learning creativity.

μ_{A2B1} : Average of students' score who take lessons with the computer media based web blog with low learning creativity.

μ_{A1B2} : Average students' score who take lessons with the power point media with high learning creativity.

μ_{A2B2} : The average of students' score who take lessons with the power point media with low learning creativity.

D. Results

First Hypothesis

Testing the hypothesis in this study was carried out using two-way ANOVA analysis, followed by the Tukey test. Furthermore, the results of data analysis with ANAVA are presented in the form of the following table.

Table 2. ANAVA calculation results with a significant

level of $\alpha = 0.05$ using SPSS 20
Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Nilai

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	177.214 ^a	3	59.071	25.031	.000
Intercept	40716.071	1	40716.071	17253.376	.000
A	12.071	1	12.071	5.115	.028
B	14.000	1	14.000	5.932	.018
A * B	151.143	1	151.143	64.047	.000
Error	122.714	52	2.360		
Total	41016.000	56			
Corrected Total	299.929	55			

a. R Squared = .591 (Adjusted R Squared = .567)

The significant level used $\alpha = 0.5$ or 5%

Basic decision making: If the value of $F < F\text{-table}$ or sig value $> \alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted. If the value of $F > F\text{-table}$ or sig value $< \alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected

Decision: Based on table 2. for testing this hypothesis is obtained

Tabel 3. Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Nilai

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
A	12.071	1	12.071	5.115	.028
Error	122.714	52	2.360		

Seen $F\text{-Count } 5.115 > F\text{-table} = 4.07$ or sig value = $0.028 < \alpha = 0.05$

Based on these results the decision is that H_0 is rejected and what is accepted is H_1 .

Conclusion: This first hypothesis is proven true, that students' English learning outcomes that follow learning with computer media based web blog (A1) are higher than the learning outcomes of students who take power point media (A2).

Second Hypothesis

The significant level used $\alpha = 0.5$ or 5%

Basic decision making:

If the value of $F < F\text{-table}$ or sig value $> \alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted

If the value of $F > F\text{-table}$ or sig value $< \alpha = 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected

Decision: Based on table 3 for testing this hypothesis is obtained

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Nilai

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
A * B	151.143	1	151.143	64.047	.000
Error	122.714	52	2.360		

Seen $F\text{-Calculate} = 64,047 > F\text{-table} = 4.07$ or $\text{sig.} = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$

Conclusion: This second hypothesis is proven by the fact that there is an influence of the interaction between computer media based web blog and learning creativity on English learning outcomes.

Third Hypothesis

The significant level used $\alpha = 0.5$ or 5%

Basic decision making: H_0 is accepted or H_0 is rejected if the value of $\text{Sig} > \alpha = 0.05$

Table 4. The results of the Tukey Test calculation with a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$ using SPSS 20 Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: A1B1,A1B2,A2B1,A2B2

Tukey HSD

(I) AB	(J) AB	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
A1B1	A1B2	4.2857*	.58063	.000	2.7447	5.8268
	A2B1	4.2143*	.58063	.000	2.6732	5.7553
	A2B2	1.9286*	.58063	.009	.3875	3.4696
A1B2	A1B1	-4.2857*	.58063	.000	-5.8268	-2.7447
	A2B1	-.0714	.58063	.999	-1.6125	1.4696
	A2B2	-2.3571*	.58063	.001	-3.8982	-.8161
A2B1	A1B1	-4.2143*	.58063	.000	-5.7553	-2.6732
	A1B2	.0714	.58063	.999	-1.4696	1.6125
	A2B2	-2.2857*	.58063	.001	-3.8268	-.7447
A2B2	A1B1	-1.9286*	.58063	.009	-3.4696	-.3875
	A1B2	2.3571*	.58063	.001	.8161	3.8982
	A2B1	2.2857*	.58063	.001	.7447	3.8268

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 2.360.

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Tukey Test Results:

Based on the results of the Tukey test, the value of Sig. <A = 0.000, so the decision: Ho is rejected and what is accepted is H1.

Decision:

This third hypothesis is proven that students' English learning outcomes that follow learning with computer media based web blog with high learning creativity (A1B1) are significantly higher than students who take learning with power point media with high learning creativity (A1B2).

Fourth Hypothesis

The significant level used $\alpha = 0.5$ or 5%

Basic decision making:

Ho is accepted or Ho is rejected if the value of Sig > $\alpha = 0.05$

Ho is accepted or Ho is rejected if the value of Sig < $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5. The results of the Tukey Test calculation with a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$ using SPSS Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: A1B1,A1B2,A2B1,A2B2
Tukey HSD

(I) AB	(J) AB	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
	A1B2	4.2857*	.58063	.000	2.7447	5.8268
A1B1	A2B1	4.2143*	.58063	.000	2.6732	5.7553
	A2B2	1.9286*	.58063	.009	.3875	3.4696
	A1B1	-4.2857*	.58063	.000	-5.8268	-2.7447
A1B2	A2B1	-.0714	.58063	.999	-1.6125	1.4696
	A2B2	-2.3571*	.58063	.001	-3.8982	-.8161
	A1B1	-4.2143*	.58063	.000	-5.7553	-2.6732
A2B1	A1B2	.0714	.58063	.999	-1.4696	1.6125
	A2B2	-2.2857*	.58063	.001	-3.8268	-.7447
	A1B1	-1.9286*	.58063	.009	-3.4696	-.3875
A2B2	A1B2	2.3571*	.58063	.001	.8161	3.8982
	A2B1	2.2857*	.58063	.001	.7447	3.8268

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 2.360.

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square (Error) = 2.360.

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Tukey Test Results:

Based on the results of the Tukey test, the value of Sig. $\alpha = 0.01$, so the decision: H_0 is rejected and what is accepted is H_1 .

Decision:

This fourth hypothesis is tested that the students' English learning outcomes of students who take lessons with computer media based web blog with low learning creativity (A1B2) are significantly lower than students who take lessons with power point media with low learning creativity (A2B2) in Indonesian subjects.

E. Discussion

Based on the hypothesis that has been carried out, the overall learning outcomes of the group of students who were taught with the computer media based web blog were higher than the English learning outcomes of the group of students who were taught with power point media. This has implications for the

English learning process, namely the need for development and application of teacher blog media as a medium and source of learning for students, especially English subjects. Learning by utilizing web blogs can improve students' creativity in developing reading

Skills. The response from readers or visitors to the blog will increase their creativity to continue to develop a culture of literacy.

During this time the teacher is more dominant using power point media as a supporter of learning media which emphasize more on the transfer of knowledge by teachers and students tend to be objects of learning. Students only receive information from one direction. Not a few of the teachers who only provided material only for students to copy again in their notebooks.

Web blog learning media provides students with wider learning space. Learning materials cannot only be accessed during teaching and learning activities in class with very limited number of face-to-face meetings. Students can access the learning resources used by teachers through web blogs media anytime, anywhere, and according to their learning needs.

Display and menu presented, in the form of subject matter, teacher work tools, practice questions, student learning outcomes in the form of student works can be a source of inspiration for students in carrying out tasks or preparing lesson material before the teaching and learning activities in the class. The work of students who are shown on the teacher's blog and get responses from readers and visitors can lead to high learning creativity for students to produce good work.

Because these two media have their respective roles in teaching and learning activities and increase students' creativity in accordance with their respective roles, there is no harm in teacher to use both media alternately as variations. Given that each teaching material has different characteristics, so do students. Therefore, with the application of more varied learning media can serve differences in the characteristics of students and teaching materials so that learning objectives can be achieved optimally.

F. Conclusion

Based on the hypothesis test as described above, the following will be concluded:

1. Overall there are significant differences between student learning outcomes who are taught with computer media based web blog and students who are taught with power point media. English learning outcomes of students who are taught with computer media based web blog are higher than students who are taught with power point media.
2. Overall there is an effect of interaction between learning media and students' creativity in English subjects.
3. Learning outcomes of students who have high creativity and are taught with computer media based web blog are higher than learning outcomes with power point media.

4. Learning outcomes of students who have low creativity and are taught with power point media are higher than learning outcomes with computer media based web blog.

In general, the conclusion of this study is that if English learning uses computer media based web blog, student learning outcomes will increase. In addition, student learning outcomes are also influenced by external factors such as the selection of learning media and the characteristics of the material to be taught.

Internal factors of students, such as the creativity of students who are individual characters are also very important factors to be considered in the effort to choose appropriate learning media to achieve maximum learning outcomes.

If external factors in the form of selecting learning media can be well organized by considering the internal factors of students, there will be an effective teaching and learning process to convey the desired learning goals and obtain maximum results.

REFERENCES

- Iwan Binanto. *Multimedia Digital: Dasar Teori dan Pengembangannya*. Yogyakarta. CV Andi Offset. .2010.
- Lodiman.Skripsi:*Peningkatan Prestasi Belajar IPA melalui Penggunaan Multimedia VCD Interaktif pada Siswa Tunagrahita Ringan Kelas XII di MALB-C Wiyata Dharma 4 Godean Tahun Ajaran 2011-2012*. [Tidak diterbitkan: FIP UNY. 2012.
- Marisa, dkk.*Komputer dan Media Pembelajaran*. Jakarta. Universitas Terbuka. 2011.
- Sudjana, Nana, *Penilaian Hasil Proses Belajar Mengajar* Bandung: PT. RemajaRosdakarya, 2006.
- SuharsimiArikunto, *Prosedur Penelitian, Suatu Pendekatan Praktek* Yogyakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2006.
- Susamo, *Penyampaian Bahan Ajaran Melalui Pemanfaatan Metode dan Media dalam Proses Pembelajaran*. Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan, Vol.10. No. 1. 2010
- Susilana, Rudi dan Riyana, Cepi, *Media Pembelajaran*, Bandung: FIP, UPI, 2008
- Widharyanto, “*Student Active Learning: Latar Belakang Kemunculan dan Prinsip-prinsipnya*”, *Jurnal Kependidikan Widya Dharma, tahun XIII, No. 1, Oktober 2002*.